

DEVELOPMENT OF PRELIMINARY STANDARD OPERATING PROCEDURE OF SURYAKSHARA SHODHANA

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ABSTRACT

Background: In Ayurveda, metals and minerals are frequently utilized for therapeutic purposes. The first step involved in processing metals and minerals is Shodhana by focusing on eliminating impurities and enhancing the properties. Which renders them appropriate for further processing. Surya kshara is a less utilized mineral, primarily affecting the mutrakricchra, mutraashmari, prameha etc. **Methods** described in Rasa Tarangini were followed to perform Nirmaleekarana and Shodhana processes, which were carried out in three batches. Organoleptic and physicochemical analysis of Surya kshara were carried out. **Results:** It was found that during procedure the crystalline Surya kshara turned into powder form after Nirmaleekarana, possessing characteristic Ela odor after Shodhana with Ela Hima. In an Analytical study, the parameters showed noticeable change, the pH of Surya kshara after Nirmaleekarana and Shodhana with a difference of 1.68

and 0.31. **Conclusion:** Shodhana of Surya kshara was done according to the reference mentioned in Rasa Tarangini. To standardize the procedure, it was done 3 times and done its preliminary study.

KEYWORDS: Surya kshara, Nirmaleekarana, Shodhana, Ela Hima, Potassium nitrate, Karpoora gandhi Shilajatu.

INTRODUCTION

Rasashastra is a field within Ayurvedic medicine that focuses specifically on the use of metals and minerals in pharmaceuticals.^[1] Kshara is one of the effective Rasaushadhis. Rasaushadhi, or medicines made from these substances, hold a prominent place in Ayurvedic practice due to their small dosage requirements, rapid effectiveness, and ability to treat severe diseases.^[2]

Surya kshara is a mineral, chemically known as Potassium nitrate (KNO_3), which has been indicated in various diseases like Vidagdhajirna, Mutrashmari, Mutrakricchra, Agnimandya, Pandu and Prameha etc. Classical Ayurvedic texts suggest that the formulations of Surya kshara are primarily used for internal consumption. It is a key ingredient in many Rasa Yogas like Shwetha parpati, Sheetala parpati, Shankha dravaka and Surakshara Kaseesa.^[3]

Potassium nitrate is an ionic salt composed of Potassium ions (K^+) and Nitrate ions (NO_3^-). It occurs naturally as a mineral called Niter and serves as a solid source of nitrogen. Potassium nitrate also known as Saltpeter is a key component in various nitrogen containing compound.^[4]

Surya kshara is a mineral not referenced in the early classical texts of Rasashastra. It appears, however, in the context of Karpooora Shilajatu, which is chemically identified as Potassium nitrate (KNO_3). Brihat Rasaraja Sundara refers to Karpooora Shilajatu by its synonyms Soraka and Sora,^[5] while the Rasa Paddhati designates it as Kshareeya Shilajatu.^[6] The Rasa Tarangini, a more recent Rasashastra text, outlines a unique procedure for its Shodhana, although there are different methods which can be used in different formulation depending upon its utility and indication. The method closely resembles the one described for Karpooora Shilajatu in the Rasa Ratna Samucchaya.^[7] Hence, in the present study, an attempt is made to authenticate and develop a preliminary standard operating procedure regarding Shodhana of Surya kshara.

METHODOLOGY

Collection of raw materials

Raw materials required for Shodhana of Surya kshara were procured from local market genuinity of the raw drugs were authenticated by Department of Rasashastra and Bhaishajya Kalpana.

A. Pharmaceutical study

Steps involved in pharmaceutical study

- Preparation of Ela Hima^[8]
- Nirmaleekarana of Surya kshara^[9]
- Shodhana of Surya kshara^[10]

Shodhana of Surya kshara and preparation of Ela hima were done in the practical laboratory, Department of Rasashastra and Bhaishajya Kalpana.

Table 1: Ingredients required for Nirmaleekarana and Shodhana of Surya kshara.

Sl. No.	Ingredients	English name	Botanical/ Chemical name	Total quantity taken
1	Surya kshara	Potassium nitrate (KNO ₃)	Potassium nitrate	600g
2	Ela	Cardamom	<i>Elettaria cardamomum (Linn.) Maton</i>	70g
3	Jala	Water (H ₂ O)	<i>Dihydrogen monoxide</i>	Quantity sufficient

Preparation of Ela Hima

20 grams of coarse Ela powder was soaked overnight in 120 ml of potable water. The next morning, it was thoroughly macerated with clean hands. After maceration, the mixture was filtered through a clean cotton cloth, and the resulting Ela Hima was used for the subsequent shodhana process.

Nirmaleekarana of Surya kshara

Nirmaleekarana is the preliminary step involved in the shodhana procedure, 200g of Surya kshara was dissolved in 800ml of potable water. The liquid was filtered once using a clean cotton cloth. The filtrate is then taken in a clean wide mouthed pan and placed over mild fire (72.4°C). The liquid was boiled and evaporated until very little quantity of liquid was left at the base of the vessel. Later, the vessel was taken out of the fire and allowed to cool on its own. Then the vessel was placed under warmer at 64.2°C to evaporate the moisture content completely. The obtained Surya kshara was weighed and stored. Precautions taken include maintaining a mild fire throughout the procedure, ensuring a small amount of liquid remains, and maintaining a warmer temperature.

Shodhana of Surya kshara

In a clean khalwa yantra, the Nirmaleekrita Surya kshara was ground into a fine powder. It was then subjected to bhavana (levigation) with Ela Hima until siddhi lakshana was achieved. Later, it was dried and stored in an airtight container. The bhavana process was repeated three times.

B. Physico-chemical study

Analyses involved in physico-chemical study

- p^H
- Loss on drying

p^H

The pH value measures acidic or alkaline of the solution. It is calculated using the formula. $p^H = -\log[H_3O^+]$, which means it depends on the concentration of hydrogen ions in the solution. The pH scale ranges from 0 to 14. A solution with a pH of 7 is neutral, while a pH below 7 indicates acidity, and a pH above 7 indicates alkalinity. This scale helps to easily determine the chemical nature of a solution.^[11]

Loss on drying

Loss on drying measures the number of volatile substances, including water, that can be removed from a material under specified conditions. This value is determined using a digital moisture meter, which calculates the loss as a reduction in weight expressed as a percentage (weight/weight or w/w). It provides insight into the amount of volatile matter that can be driven off during the drying process, following a standardized procedure.

Procedure: To determine the loss on drying, 1 gram of the sample was placed directly onto the moisture meter's plate. The lid of the moisture meter was closed, and heating was initiated by pressing the start button. The volatile matter or moisture, if present, was evaporated and dried at a temperature of $105^\circ\text{C} \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$. Once the process was completed, the final reading was recorded. This reading was subtracted from 100 to calculate the loss on drying at the specified temperature.^[12]

Table No 2: Showing the Guna-Karma of the drugs.

Sl. No.	Materials	Rasa	Guna	Veerya	Karma	Rogagnatha
1	Surya kshara ^[13]	Katu, Lavana	Tikshna, Sara	Ushna	Agni deepana	Vidagdhajirna, Mutrashmari, Mutrakricchra, Agnimandya, Pandu, Prameha
2	Ela ^[14]	Katu, Madhura	Laghu	Sheeta	Rochana, Deepana, Anulomana, Hridya, Mutrala	Kasa, Shwasa, Aruchi, Chardi, Mutrakricchra
3	Jala ^[15]	Avyaktha rasa	Laghu	Sheeta	Pittahara, Jeevana, Tarpana, Hridya	

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

Table 3: Preparation of Ela Hima.

Sample	Bhavana	Ela (weight)	Water (volume)	Obtained Ela Hima (volume)
Sample 1	1 st bhavana	10g	60ml	56ml
	2 nd bhavana	8g	48ml	45ml
	3 rd bhavana	7g	42ml	40ml
Sample 2	1 st bhavana	8g	48ml	46ml
	2 nd bhavana	7g	42ml	39ml
	3 rd bhavana	8g	48ml	45ml
Sample 3	1 st bhavana	8g	48ml	45ml
	2 nd bhavana	7g	42ml	40ml
	3 rd bhavana	7g	42ml	39ml
Total		70g	420ml	395ml

Note: g= grams, ml= milliliter

Table 4: Observations and results during the process of Nirmaleekarana and Shodhana.

Sample	Bhavana	Ashuddha Surya kshara (weight)	Weight of Surya kshara after nirmaleekarana	Ela Hima (volume)	Duration of bhavana	Weight of Surya kshara after shodhana
Sample 1	1 st bhavana	200g	196g	40ml	1 hour	194g
	2 nd bhavana		194g	38ml	1 hour	190g
	3 rd bhavana		190g	30ml	1 hour	185g
Sample 2	1 st bhavana	200g	197g	36ml	1 hour	195g
	2 nd bhavana		195g	35ml	1 hour	192g
	3 rd bhavana		192g	39ml	1 hour	190g
Sample 3	1 st bhavana	200g	195g	35ml	1 hour	191g
	2 nd bhavana		191g	36ml	1 hour	189g
	3 rd bhavana		189g	32ml	1 hour	187g

Note: g= gram, ml= milliliter

Table 5: Results of pharmaceutical study.

Samples	Ashuddha Surya kshara (weight)	After nirmaleekarana (weight)	Loss after nirmaleekarana (weight)	After shodhana (weight)	Loss after shodhana (weight)	Loss after shodhana (percentage)
Sample 1	200g	196g	4g	185g	15g	7.5%
Sample 2	200g	197g	3g	190g	10g	5%
Sample 3	200g	195g	5g	187g	13g	6.5%
Total				562g	38g	6.33%

Note: g = gram

Three samples of Ashuddha Suryakshara showed a consistent reduction in weight during both Nirmaleekarana and Shodhana processes. In Sample 1, the initial weight of 200 g reduced to 196 g after Nirmaleekarana, indicating a loss of 4 g, and further decreased to 185 g after

Shodhana, with a total loss of 15 g (7.5%). Sample 2 showed a similar trend, with a 3 g reduction after Nirmaleekarana and a total loss of 10 g after Shodhana, corresponding to 5%. Sample 3 exhibited the highest loss during Nirmaleekarana (5g) and a total reduction of 13 g after Shodhana, amounting to 6.5%. Overall, the combined weight loss after Shodhana across all samples was 38 g, with an average percentage loss of approximately 6.33%. These findings highlight that both purification steps contribute to measurable reductions in weight, reflecting the removal of impurities and refinement of the raw material.

Table 6: Organoleptic characteristics of Surya kshara.

Parameters	Ashuddha Surya kshara	Nirmaleekrita Surya kshara	Shodhita Surya kshara	Ela Hima
Color	Bright white	Bright white	Dull white	Dusty
Odour	Characteristic odour	Characteristic odour	Alkaline with characteristic odour of Ela	Characteristic odour
Taste	Pungent alkaline	Pungent alkaline	Pungent alkaline with characteristic taste of Ela	Characteristic taste
Touch	Rough with sharp edges	Smooth	Smooth	-
Appearance	White crystalline form	White powder form	Dull white powder form	Liquid consistency

The parameters of Surya Kshara samples were carefully noted and compared at different stages. The Ashuddha Surya Kshara had a bright white color, characteristic odour, pungent alkaline taste, rough touch with sharp edges, and appeared in a crystalline form. After Nirmaleekarana, the material retained its bright white color and characteristic odour, but its texture became smooth and its appearance changed to a white powder form, while the taste remained pungent alkaline. Following Shodhana, the sample turned dull white in color, carried an alkaline odour along with the characteristic fragrance of Ela, and exhibited a pungent alkaline taste with the distinct flavor of Ela. Its texture remained smooth, but the appearance shifted to a dull white powder form. In contrast, Ela Hima was observed to be dusty in color, had a characteristic odour, displayed a characteristic taste, and showed liquid consistency.

Table 7: Physico-chemical analysis of Surya kshara.

	Ashuddha Surya kshara	Nirmaleekrita Surya kshara			Shodhita Surya kshara			Ela Hima
		Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3	
pH	6.14	7.95	7.82	7.70	6.42	6.38	6.55	5.24
LOD	10.2%	-	-	-	20.2%	21.6%	18.8%	-
Average pH of Nirmaleekrita Surya kshara					7.82			
Average pH of Shodhita Surya kshara					6.45			
Average Loss on drying of Shodhita Surya kshara					20.2%			

Note: LOD= Loss on drying

The pH and loss on drying (LOD) values of Surya Kshara samples were systematically observed at different stages. The Ashuddha Surya Kshara showed a pH of 6.14, while the Nirmaleekrita Surya Kshara samples recorded pH values of 7.95, 7.82, and 7.70, with an average of 7.82. The Shodhita Surya Kshara samples exhibited slightly lower pH values of 6.42, 6.38, and 6.55, giving an average of 6.45. The Ela Hima sample showed a pH of 5.24. In terms of LOD, the Ashuddha Surya Kshara had 10.2%, whereas the Shodhita Surya Kshara samples demonstrated higher values of 20.2%, 21.6%, and 18.8%, with an average of 20.2%. These observations indicated that the purification processes altered both the pH and moisture content of the samples, with Shodhana leading to a reduction in alkalinity and an increase in loss on drying.

DISCUSSION

Shodhana is an essential intermediary pharmaceutical process used for purification of metals and minerals during their conversion and usage into different dosage forms and purposes. There are different types of shodhana mentioned according to different metals and minerals, such as bhavana, nirvapana, dalana, and swedana etc. Nirmaleekarana often serves as a preliminary step before shodhana processes. By removing physical impurities, it prepares the material for more intensive purification methods, enhancing the overall effectiveness of the shodhana. This step is essential to ensure that the substances are free from contaminants that could potentially harm the body.

After nirmaleekarana, Surya kshara lost its crystalline structure as it was dissolved in water. In addition, it became brighter after nirmaleekarana as the impurities were filtered off and after shodhana; it lost its brightness and turned into a dull white color due to the addition of Ela Hima, which was of dusty color. The loss in weight of sample 1, 2 and 3 after nirmaleekarana was 4g, 3g, and 5g respectively. This suggests the quantity of impurities present in Surya kshara. The weight loss observed after shodhana was due to spillage and loss in khalwa yantra during the bhavana process. All three samples of nirmaleekrita Surya kshara consumed a varied quantity of Ela Hima for each bhavana. This may be because of the varied amount of moisture present in Surya kshara after nirmaleekarana.

Ela Hima was freshly prepared each time for each bhavana. Bhavana Dravya helps in minimizing or neutralizing the toxic properties of a raw material. Additionally, the Bhavana

process leads to the incorporation of organic compounds into the mineral, enhancing its potency. This phenomenon not only helps in removing soluble impurities but also adds beneficial materials to the drug, thereby improving its overall efficacy. Ela Hima helps in neutralizing the alkaline property of the drug. During the process of shodhana, Surya kshara was given bhavana with Ela Hima for 1 hour. However, there were no subhavitha lakshana observed and it did not get dried completely, as it is kshara which is hygroscopic in nature and has no binding property within it.

As the name suggests, kshara should have an alkaline p^H , but ashuddha Surya kshara possessed a p^H of 6.14, which suggests it is a weak acid. But the process of nirmaleekarana increased the p^H to 7.82 that is alkaline by removing the physical impurities present in it. However, the p^H again decreased to 6.45 at the end of shodhana because of the addition of Ela Hima for bhavana, which was of p^H 5.24. The average p^H of Shodhitha Surya kshara (6.45) is near to neutral p^H , suggesting it's safer use. The non-uniform drying of Surya kshara leads to varied values of loss on drying, which was due to the hygroscopic nature of Surya kshara. This is the preliminary study on suryakshara with no previous study so far.

CONCLUSION

Surya Kshara is a mineral known for its beneficial effects in treating conditions such as Vidagdhajirna, Mutrashmari, Mutrakricchra, Agnimandya, Pandu, and Prameha. However, using any mineral without proper Shodhana can be harmful, potentially leading to minor health issues or even severe complications. Therefore, the Shodhana process for Surya Kshara is crucial to ensure its safety and efficacy. In this study, the process of Nirmaleekarana and shodhana of Surya kshara were done three times and attempts were made to develop preliminary standard operative procedures.

LIMITATION: The study was conducted on a small number of samples, which may not represent wider variability. Only pH and loss on drying (LOD) were analyzed, leaving out other important physicochemical parameters. Advanced instrumental techniques were not employed, limiting the precision and depth of characterization.

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AUTHOR'S CONTRIBUTION

First author: Review of the work, analysis and interpretation of the data.

Corresponding author: Editing the work

Second author: Final approval of the work for publication.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The authors decline that the data supporting the findings of this study are available within the paper and its supplementary information files.

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